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¹ **Deliverable Type:**

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

² **Dissemination Level:**

PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
CO: Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
EU-RES: Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)
EU-CON: Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)
EU-SEC: Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)

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Executive Summary

Arctichub videobox aims to summarize the current state of development of new and existing economic activities (e.g., forestry, mining, fish farming, tourism and indigenous activities including reindeer herding and hunting) in few selected hubs in the Arctic; and illustrate local people's perceived present and future development of the hubs. The target audience of the videos is the general public with its core messages based entirely on local situation of the hubs. In collaboration with selected project partners, we created a total of five (5) videos: 2 videos for Varangerfjord based on stakeholder interviews and future scenario work; 1 video for Gällivare based on the results of Q-study's current perspectives on development of economic activities; 1 video for Westfjords based on the result of Qstudy and future scenario work; and 1 Arctic overall video based on key findings from Q-study conducted in all ArcticHubs project sites. These videos utilized a combination of whiteboard animation, interview-style footage, and open-source videos, integrating both interviews and animations to capitalize on the strengths of each approach. Videos were created using VideoScribe and Da Vince Resolve, and were posted in YouTube via BOKU University YouTube channel. The videobox serves as bases for discussion in WP5 future forums and as communication device by the communities once the project is finished to continue the dialogue.

1. Videobox Objective

WP3 developed a videobox or a series of five videos that showcases how selected Arctic hubs/communities perceive their present and future development based on the work done in tasks 3.1.-3.5 and WP5 (D5.1 Future scenario reports). The aim of the videobox is to:

1. Summarize the current state of development of new and existing economic activities (e.g., forestry, mining, fish farming, tourism and indigenous activities including reindeer herding and hunting) in few selected hubs in Arctic; and
2. Illustrate local people's perceived present and future development of the hubs

The resulting short videos can be used to present research results in a different way than a report and serves as bases for discussion in WP5 future forums and follow up research. The videobox can also be a communication device by the communities themselves once the project is finished to continue the dialogue.

The **target audience** of the videobox is the **general public** to increase awareness and knowledge about the local stakeholders' present and future perception of development in the Arctic, and that it may deviate from their own view of the Arctic. Videos are also targeted at industry employees, experts and managers who can learn about specific localized issues, as these videos will be posted in YouTube and shared via social media platforms and other channels in order to reach wide audience from youth to older people.

The **core messages** of the videobox are based entirely on presenting local situation of the hubs. All the five videos in the series contain most of the following main points:

- The Arctic is often perceived to host only pristine nature and nomadic indigenous groups, in reality, economic activities are proliferating due to global drivers and pressures and increasing accessibility of the region (Zivojinovic et al 2022; Suopajärvi et al 2022).
- Economic industries such as forestry, mining, fish farming and tourism provide economic benefits but can have negative environmental and socioeconomic impacts (Zivojinovic et al 2022; Zivojinovic et al forthcoming).
- Indigenous activities such as reindeer husbandry, fishing and hunting are affected by the global pressures, climate change, green transition and the negative environmental impacts of all the industries (Flick et al 2022; Suopajärvi et al 2022).
- Local residents have diverse perspectives on the current state and future prospects of the Arctic and their local regions. How to balance and include these various perspectives in decision making and policy creation is a challenge (Elomina et al 2024; Tuulentie et al 2023).

2. Content

The **duration** of each video is **5 - 10 mins** focusing on five selected locations in the Arctic hubs project. Table 1 provides a summary of location and content of the five videos included in the videobox. The main content of the videos is based from the Q-study³ results (WP3.3) and future scenario⁴ report (WP5). However, the content of each video varies depending on the availability of materials and the methods used, as discussed below:

2.1. Varangerfjord, Norway (2 videos)

Two videos were created for Varangerfjord hub due to the availability of stakeholders and their willingness to participate in filming. The first video consists of interviews of stakeholders and experts discussing about how they perceive the present and future of Varangerfjord, for more detail, the script is available as appendix I. Interviews with local stakeholders were conducted instead of a Q-study to collect current perspectives. This is to avoid stakeholders' fatigue in the hub, since other studies have been conducted in the area e.g., PPGIS survey, future workshops, stakeholders' meetings, etc. The second video focuses on the future scenarios of Varangerfjord developed from the future scenario work conducted by WP5 which used PPGIS survey, workshops and scenario shaping workshop. We summarized the steps and results, and showcased it in whiteboard animation format, see script in appendix II.

2.2. Gällivare Sweden (1 video)

The video content is based on the key findings from Q-study conducted in Gällivare, Sweden. Q-study provided local stakeholders' current perspectives on development. The results were then condensed and summarized to be animated in a whiteboard animation. Although we conducted some filming in Gällivare during a research visit, some stakeholders opted out of the final video as they were reluctant to represent their organizations or groups. However, we incorporated landscape and industry video clips that we filmed to bring the realities of these environments closer to the audience. The script is available in appendix III.

2.3. Westfjords, Iceland (1 video)

The video content is based on Q-study and future scenario report. Westfjords is a study site where both research methods took place (Q-study and future scenario) and we summarized the results and showcased them in a whiteboard animation format. The script is available in appendix IV. The Q-study provided local perspectives on development based on surveys and in-person workshop with the local participants. Following these perspectives, future scenario

³ Q-study – a mixed method to study perspectives which was used for this project to determine how local people perceive the development of their hubs and the Arctic (Elomina et al 2024).

⁴ Based on systematic study of possible, probable, and preferable futures, and analysis of their potential impacts on society. Several methods have been used in the foresight work. These include Delphi method, scenario planning methods, future workshops and scanning the changes in operational environment (Tuulentie et al, 2023).

were presented that are based on forecast survey building, future workshops and Maptionnaire survey with local participants. For Westfjords, we used open-source videos to show the landscape and industry activities.

2.4. Arctic overall (1 video)

The video content is based only on Q-study describing our Arctic overall key findings, from all the ArcticHub project location⁵ which shows a more general perspective than the local ones. However, we find the results relevant as major decision makers are part of this study and general patterns are relevant for future decision making, see report D3.4 for more details. Moreover, we also used a combination of videos we filmed ourselves and open source videoclips to provide more context and real situation in the area.

Table 1. Summary of location and content of the videobox

Location	Economic activities in focus	Content	Partners	Video link
Varangerfjord, Norway	Fish farming and Tourism	Interviews, future and current development	NOFIMA, BOKU, TouchTD	https://youtu.be/ba7sPEN0OPw
		Future scenarios	NOFIMA, BOKU, TouchTD	https://youtu.be/YnBBGGkYE8o
Gällivare, Sweden	Forestry, Mining, Indigenous (tourism)	Current perspectives	BOKU, SLU	https://youtu.be/fJaqGVk5yUM
Westfjords, Iceland	Fish farming and Tourism	Current and future scenarios	BOKU, HU, UI	https://youtu.be/l3_8NI1A5I0
Arctic overall	Fish farming, forestry, mining, tourism, indigenous activity	Current perspectives	BOKU	https://youtu.be/49C03XXPzms

NOFIMA - Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research; **BOKU** - University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna; **TouchTD** - Communication and Dissemination team; **SLU** - Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences; **HU** - Holar University; **UI** - University of Iceland

⁵ Arctic Locations include Finland (Kemi, Kemijärvi, Inari, Kittilä), Sweden (Jokkmokk, Malå, Gran, Gällivare) Norway (Kautokeino-Kvalsund, Varangerfjord, Svalbard, Egersund), Iceland (Westfjords), Greenland (Nuup Kangerlua), Suðuroy (Faroe Islands)

3. Visual styles

The videos were created using various visual styles, integrating both interview footage and animations to leverage the strengths of each approach, as detailed in Table 2. For the animated segments, we primarily used whiteboard animation, as it effectively explains the complex ideas, steps, and methods of the project, please see figure 1 for a whiteboard animation sample.

Table 2. Visual styles employed in the videobox and their pros and cons

Video Style	Pros	Cons
Interview videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single person focus • Establishes expertise on a topic • Popular for thought leadership • Captures emotions and real human elements • Great for audience who cares about the topic • Can focus on advice, trends etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lacks visual stimuli • Limited audience engagement • Harder to demonstrate complex or abstract ideas compared to on screen graphics
Animated Video (e.g., Whiteboard animation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Great for explainer videos and stories • Engaging and entertaining • Good at illustrating concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long time to produce • Needs a lot of expertise • Does not capture real human emotions

Source: Walters, 2023

Figure 1. Whiteboard animation screenshot, Varangerfjord future scenarios

In addition, we used landscape and industry videos or photos to provide an idea and context of how the landscape and activities look like in real life, so the audience can get more authentic experience. These videoclips are from footages that we filmed ourselves on field trips during project lifetime and/or from open sources, to avoid copyright issues.

4. Music and Language

4.1. Music

Various musical styles were selected to match the tone of the videos. The music helped highlight the different moments of the video and the selection was done by the editor/layout expert from BOKU using royalty-free libraries.

4.2. Language

Since the target audience of the videobox is the general public, we used English as a base and to have greater reach. However, as the Arctic is multilingual, we uploaded the video in YouTube so that the audience can have an option to watch the video with their preferred subtitles i.e., Swedish, Finnish, Danish, Norwegian, Icelandic, etc. YouTube automatic translation has 100 languages available and can be viewed using laptop, phone or tablets.

Additionally, to make sure that the audience know about this option, we included an instruction in the description of each video, as follows:

“To translate the subtitles/caption, please click the 'CC' button to turn on the closed captions, and YouTube will automatically generate English captions. Step 2: Now, select the 'Settings' option — which is typically located next to 'CC' and looks like a cogwheel, then choose 'Auto-translate.' Step 3: Here, you'll see over 100 translation languages, choose the language you prefer (i.e., Norwegian, Danish, Finnish, Swedish, Icelandic)”

5. Distribution

We used YouTube platform to distribute the videos, and in particular via BOKU University YouTube channel. This is based on the advantages as enumerated in Table 3. Through YouTube, we generated links that can be posted to our and various others social media account and project website to disseminate the videos more broadly. The videos were also uploaded to Tiimeri – ArcticHubs project’ database for access of all members. Videos will also be shown at the final project meeting and future scenario workshops with local stakeholders, and will be provided to the local project partners and local communities involved in the research for further dissemination and use.

Table 3. Distribution platform used

Characteristics	Youtube	Social media (e.g.Facebook)	Project Website
Audience reach	High	High	Low
Organic reach	Great	Poor	Poor
Analytics	User friendly	User friendly	-
Customization	limited	limited	Unlimited
Costs	Free	Free	Free
Pre-roll Ads	✓	✓	X
Language versions (CC)	Automatic	Manually	Manually
Searchable	Searchable in google	Will not show in google search	Searchable in google

Source: YouTube, 2024; Meta 2024; and LUKE, 2021

All the YouTube links to the videos are available in a playlist, link here:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL8nmJRi21moHfuT8GKafERo3n6BcWm4jW>

6. Production

Since the project has limited resources for videobox development, we employed different strategies to produce the videos, as detailed below:

1. **Varangerfjord:** NOFIMA organized trips and filming with the local stakeholders on March 2022 and on June 2023. They filmed the landscape, industry activities and interviews in partnership with a local filmmaker and colleague. The interviews were not scripted and allowed participants to speak their mind. We also added our footage that was filmed on April 2024 to complete the overall video. This strategy is the most efficient as it used local talent and resources, however the resulting videos are long and they sometimes lack continuity and consistency.
2. **Gällivare:** BOKU organized a research visit on March and December 2023. We filmed the landscape, industry activities and stakeholders, using our own equipment (e.g., camera, mic, etc). This strategy is costly and required more coordination work, but produced footages that we used not only for Gällivare video but also for the Arctic video. However, some local stakeholders consented to being filmed, but only for personal use and not for public dissemination. Thus, we had to rely on the results of our analysis instead.
3. **Westfjords:** BOKU collaborated TouchTD, Holar University and University of Iceland to develop the video. However, due to limited time and resources, we were unable to organize a filming schedule in Westfjords. AS a result, we primarily used whiteboard animation and open-source videoclips to produce the video.
4. **Arctic:** We used available videoclips from Varangerfjord, Gällivare and other available clips we could find from open sources. Some videos we took from other trips were also considered but the editor decides which fits better for the tone of the project. As much as possible, we did not use any photos to create the video.

6.1. Softwares used

For the animation, we utilized the paid version of Videoscribe – a software for creating whiteboard animation (Sparkol 2024) – for nearly all the videos. To facilitate this process, BOKU enlisted a graphic designer to illustrate the animation content. The graphic designer worked closely with BOKU researchers, who helped translate the results of the Q-study and future scenarios into animation concepts.

For the voice over, we used the paid version of DaVinci Resolve Studio 18.6.5 (Blackmagic Design 2024) hosted by BOKU. DaVinci is a color grading, color correction, visual effects, and audio post-production video editing application. The voiceover was generated through AI in the software and was used in our final videos. This provided easier editing opportunities and it is more cost effective.

6.2. Limitation

During the production of the five videos in this Videobox, we encountered several limitations: Participant willingness to be filmed posed a challenge to our initial plan of creating more interview-style videos. Some local stakeholders were uncomfortable speaking on camera, and in some cases, obtaining consent from companies was too complex, with some companies ultimately refusing to participate in interviews. In Gällivare, some local stakeholders consented to being filmed only for personal use and not for public dissemination.

Additionally, due to limited time and resources; as well as delayed and prolonged data collection process than initially anticipated, we were only able to select a few study sites for inclusion in the videobox. To address this issue, we consulted with our project partners to determine who would like to participate in the video development. Those who opted in were featured in the videobox, including Varangerfjord partners at NOFIMA; Westfjord partners at Holar University and University of Iceland; and Gällivare partners at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences. The primary reasons for not including other partners were to avoid stakeholder fatigue, limited time available for coordinating with stakeholders, and insufficient financial resources for organizing travel. To mitigate these issues, we created animations based on our study results. Additionally, we plan to develop further animated videos even after the deadline of the project deliverable. We will present the remaining videos along with the final policy recommendations, that are that are still to be developed by the end of the project.

7. Post production

BOKU media team were in-charge of the post-production or editing of the videos. BOKU media team is a separate office and we hired them for editing services which is relatively cheaper than hiring private firms. Additionally, this means easier communication especially regarding revision and feedback.

The editing of the video clips was performed using the paid version of DaVinci Resolve Studio 18.6.5 (Blackmagic Design, 2024) hosted by BOKU. The editor/layout artist edited the video and sent it to BOKU researchers for feedback. We then reviewed the specific sections of the video we wanted to change and provided suggestions and additional materials as necessary. Generally, we aimed for 4 to 5 revision requests, although this varied if further corrections were needed. Additionally, we held about five face-to-face meetings with the editor to facilitate more dynamic discussions.

Finally, once the videos were finalized, they were also sent to project partners involved for feedback. Their comments were taken in consideration in the editing and revision process of the videos.

References

- Blackmagic Design Pty. Ltd. (2024) Davinci Resolve Studio 18.6.5
<https://www.blackmagicdesign.com/products/davinciresolve>
- Elomina, J., Živojinović, I., Calanasan, K.C., Dabic, I., Ivanovic, S., Pülzl, H., Lindau, A., Vacik, H., Giardino, M., Beltramo, R., Sandström, P., Sandström, S., Lidestav, G., Rikkonen, T., Tuulentie, S., Inkilä, E., Olafsdottir, R., Edvardsdóttir, A.G., Bogadóttir, R., Pállsdóttir Vang, E., Lyngge-Pedersen, K., Tjåland, Ulf., Engen, S., Nygaard, V., Rautio, P., (2024) D3.4 Synthesis report comparative analysis on socio-cultural effects. Horizon 2020 project. Grant 869580 ArcticHubs project.
- Flick, H., Teräs, J., and Ellingsen, MB. (2022) Changes in the Arctic Environment as result of hub activity, D 2.3, Horizon 2020 project. Grant 869580 ArcticHubs project.
- LUKE (2021) Arctic hub locations. <https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/hubs/> Accessed: 22 May 2024
- Meta (2024) Facebook characteristics. <https://about.meta.com/company-info/> Accessed; 22 May 2024
- Sparkol Limited (2024): VideoScribe 2 Redcliffe Way, Bristol, BS1 6NL, UK.
<https://www.videoscribe.co/>
- Suopajarvi, L.; Nygaard, V.; Guðrún Edvardsdóttir, A.; Iversen, A.; Kyllönen KM.; Lesser, P. et al. (2022): Global economic drivers in the development of different industrial hubs in the European Arctic. Arctichubs project deliverable. Horizon2020. University of Lapland.
- Tuulentie, S., Rikkonen, P., Rikkonen, T., Inkilä, E., Lyngge-Pedersen, K., Lidestav, G., Sandström, P., Sandström, S., Iversen, A., Robertsen, R., Bogadóttir, R., Vang, E., Ólafsdóttir, R., Edvardsdóttir, A.G., Bishop, M., Miettinen, J., Pasi Rautio (2023) D 5.1 Future scenario reports. Grant 869580 ArcticHubs project.
- Walters, Kendall (2023) How to Choose the Right Style of Video Every Time. Vidyard.com
<https://www.vidyard.com/blog/different-styles-of-videos/> Accessed: March 2023
- YouTube (2024) Inside YouTube. <https://blog.youtube/inside-youtube/> Accessed 22 May 2024
- YouTube (2024) Whiteboard animatio. Insurance. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1HcWhJy7mBU>
Accessed 04 Mar 2023.
- Živojinović, I.; Elomina, J.; Moioli, S.; Calanasan, K. C.; Pülzl, H.; Lidestav, G. et al. (2022): Report about context and effects of existing and new economic activities on local societies and cultures. Arctichubs project deliverable. Horizon2020. University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, BOKU.
- Živojinović, I.; Elomina, J.; Moioli, S.; Calanasan, K. C.; Pülzl, H.; Lidestav, G. et al. (forthcoming): Exploring land use conflicts arising from economic activities and their impacts on local communities in the European Arctic. Journal of Land Use Science.

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Appendix I. Varangerfjord stakeholders' perception on development

This video is part of the video box developed in the Arctic hubs project: Global drivers local consequences, tools for Global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic hubs.

Situated about 400 km Northeast of the Arctic Circle lies the Varanger peninsula.

The region is home to several industries that while contributing to its local economy can also have adverse environmental effects. These industries include fishing, aquaculture and tourism.

As most Arctic towns are perceived to host only pristine nature and nomadic indigenous Groups. In reality economic activities are proliferating due to global drivers and pressures

The Varanger region is part of the research project ArcticHubs.

Statement Jerbelle Elomina, BOKU

“In the Arctic Hub projects we aim to develop sustainable and solution-oriented responses to the current trends and um challenges in the Arctic and in particular in this case it's the Varangerfjord Hub and of course in our work we also aim to reconcile this kind of competing livelihoods and land use modes like fish farming and tourism”.

As a fjord near the coast, fishing is a traditional economic activity in the area. However, challenges arise from different sea use of the fish farming, aquaculture and tourism industry.

Statement Erling Haugan, Norwegian King Crab Fisherman

“Today it's the biggest export article from Bugøynes – its king crab. So actually, its going all around the world. It was in the end of 2000 we started to export live king crab- and today I think 95% of all crabs are exported alive around the world – United States, to South Korea, to Asia and a little bit, something is also going to Europe.”

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Statement Roy Robertson, NOFIMA

“For the time being, it’s a little bit a battle about access to the sea, especially for the aquaculture. Even though the aquaculture don’t use a lot of space, it’s only 5 km² where the sites are in different localities and the fjord is 3,200 km² so there it’s a huge Fjord.”

Statement Sten Siikavuopio, NOFIMA

“You will see in the future that more of the salmon producer want to produce the salmon in the north because the temperature and the climate is better there. The local fishman will feel the pressure from new industry that want to come into this area. Due to the climate changes and there is, you know there’s a lot of space left there – so but at the same time it’s very important here for the local fisheries.”

Statement Erling Haugan, Statement Erling Haugan, Norwegian King Crab Fisherman

“Do you think there is room for more aquaculture in Varanger?”

Of course, I think so yes but I don’t hope it will be more

I feel that they are a little bit arrogant with us. They don’t want to talk with us and to actually do what whatever they want. And for me, I own this boat myself and all my money is going back to my little small village and I feel that this, uh, aquaculture company, they are owned by a man in, maybe in Dubai or in London or actually wherever.”

Statement Jørn Olaf Malinen

“We are now, uh, yeah. Fighting for the for the situation to keep fishermen here in this area. And there are upcoming a lot of industry that we want to have part to this king crab”

Besides the locals and the large seafood companies have very different interests, there are also other interests in the use of the sea in the fjords.

Tourist come to Varangerfjord to fish and experience small town living...

Statement Jerbelle Elomina, BOKU

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“So, it was really important for us in BOKU to talk to the local people, to hear from them, to really have an understanding of what is the current situation in Varanger and it was thanks to our project Partners in NOFIMA that we get to be connected to the local community.”

Statement Trond Høiberget, visit Bugøynes

“It's possible in small society like those in the end of the world, in the end of the road to do something that people come to, to enjoy. In our company Visit Bugøynes we have in a way five branch and that's bed, boat, bistro, sauna and safaris.”

Statement Pål Haldorsen, Vranger Brygge

“Last summer or last spring, we got our first four boats. Now you only see two of them because two of them are outside. I have a German group here.

When I grew up it was 360 -70 people living between us, 60 kids on the school. Now it's more 170 and 15 kids on the school. So that's not nice to know that the population is going down. But we wanted to buy some house, rebuild them, totally renovated and make life in the house Okay. For some years it will be our guests. Yes, but even though it's light, instead of being darkness.

We have to do something for the future. “

One important aspect is consideration for local structures and sustainable growth, especially in tourism.

Statement Trond Høiberget, Visit Bugøynes

“The Sea has to be the nerve in our activity - what we get from the sea is also what we need to serve our guests. And that's the reason we only have local food, local resources.”

Statement Pål Haldorsen, Vranger Brygge

“We don't hire out the houses for one night. Sorry. If you want only one night, please go to two or something else. We only renting out for more than two days or more.”

Statement Trond Høiberget, Visit Bugøynes

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“It's it's not good for our society that it's only a couple of places to work, together a society which can grow and expand. We need different kind of activities. People who can be nursing and mechanic in the company, in a partnership, and then they bring kids to the to the village. So, the big, big challenge is to get new people coming to stay and to produce kids. That's the future.”

Statement Roy Robertsen, NOFIMA

“The Varangerfjord hub in 2035 are growing related to industries and is maybe more acceptable for that due to the need of working places, the value creation, the activity... there has to be a positive development for aquaculture, all the signs that uh the world need more food, fish and so on and the natural stocks has been uh very good in the area but there are some wild cards here, it could be the climate, that the natural uh stocks in the fields move away or we don't get this the migrating fish stocks that are coming into the into the fjords”

Statement Jerbelle Elomina, BOKU

“It was really insightful to talk to the local people, to the local experts and to the local entrepreneurs and learn about how the local people really see the current development of the industries in Varangerfjord Hub and also particularly how they foresee the future of the industries in their area. And this is very important for us because it is one of the outcomes of our study and of course lastly the outcomes of this study which is of course learning about the local based solutions and the current views will be used in developing policy guidelines.”

There are different perspectives and different visions on how Varangerfjord's industries should develop. But what stands out is, the locals are doing their part for their community, sustaining Varangerfjords' vitality and growth.

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Appendix II. Future scenarios on Varangerfjord development

A video series developed by Global drivers, local consequences: Tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic “hubs” (ArcticHubs)

Future scenarios on Varangerfjord development

Situated about 400 km northeast of the Arctic Circle lies Varangerfjord

The fjord is home to several industries that while contributing to its local economy, can also have adverse environmental effects. These industries include fishing, aquaculture, and tourism

As most Arctic towns are perceived to host only pristine nature and nomadic indigenous groups. In reality, economic activities are proliferating due to global drivers and pressures.

The future is uncertain, but Arctichubs project can provide the background and the venue so people can see how their decisions could turn out in the future...

Based on Arctichubs reports, surveys and the knowledge from decision-makers, authorities, economic actors, and local residents including indigenous peoples, we developed future stories or scenarios about how Varangerfjord would look like in the future?

Through a series of workshops and discussion rounds with local stakeholders, we found 5 future scenarios

Varangerfjord’s future scenarios

the first scenario ‘Green growth’ describes a future where the need for new solutions have resulted in economic growth and optimism in the region, and Varangerfjord is the starting point for transportation of goods through the east passage, from west to east.

Both fisheries and aquaculture have developed positively. Global warming has impacts on wild fish stocks and winter tourism.

the second scenario ‘Arctic Urbanity’ represents a vision how people-oriented change based on identity and culture may drive development.

In this scenario, the key concerns are attracting young people to the area

the third scenario ‘Traditionalist Trap’ is the preservation of traditional industries, which restricts the growth of new industries with young, educated workforce.

the fourth scenario ‘Ghost Town’: the increasing demand for food and economic growth, and climate change has put too much pressure on the area, resulting to an environmentally unsustainable use of the resources of the fjord, with loss of ecosystem services.

This has implications on the economic and social situation, as well as the cultural identity, and the demand for resources drivers into geopolitical conflicts transforming Varanger into a military defense hub.

the fifth scenario 'Emerging Coexistence' is the social license for aquaculture, which results in a successful coexistence between the new and traditional industries, where cooperation between different industries creates synergies.

The scenarios addressed both the opportunities and threats to Varangerfjord, which also applies to the development of the industries and the effects of global drivers, green growth and climate change to the fjord.

What these future scenarios bring on the forefront can put pressures on local decision-makers and to the need to combine the wider global change to local way of life.

Thus, the ArcticHubs future work process continues by evaluating the scenarios made and introducing them to the decisionmakers and raising a discussion how to consider them in land use planning and in developing livelihood.

Global drivers. Local consequences

Appendix III. Current perspectives on Gällivare development

This video is part of the videobox developed in the Arctichubs project:

Global drivers, local consequences: Tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic “hubs”

Current perspectives on Gällivare development

If you look up arctic images in the internet, you will always find three things: snow covered landscapes with the northern lights, polar bears and vast wilderness without any sign of human activity. But in reality, this is not the case.

Gällivare is a town a hundred kilometers north of the arctic circle. Though Gällivare may look sparsely populated and vacant, 80% of these lands are being used, for forestry, reindeer husbandry, mining, and other uses...

There’s a lot of expansion of economic activities behind those snow-covered landscape due to globalization. There’s mining, forestry, tourism and energy sector just to name a few. There are actual towns here too, where locals and indigenous Sami people live; and they are affected by the development of economic activities, like in the case of Gällivare.

But what do local people really think about the development in Gällivare, Sweden?

To answer our question, we conducted Q methodology

Q methodology is a mixed method to study perspectives. It is done in 5 steps. First, determining the universe of opinions regarding Gällivare development based on expert interviews and literature review. Then we selected sample opinions focusing on forestry, mining and reindeer husbandry. Third, we tested 36 sampled opinions or Q-set with a group of participants- these are experts, authorities, local citizens and special ones that stand to gain or lose whatever the result of the development. We then conducted an online and in-person survey. A total of 22 participants sorted and ranked them in an inverted grid to most agree to disagree. Once all the survey were collected, we ran statistical analysis composed of different steps, after which we extracted three perspectives

Current perspectives on Gällivare’s development

The first perspective, Ambivalence to growth, Advocates simultaneously experience opposing or contradictory views on industries.

They believe that Gällivare thrives only because of the mines and the current social transformation will provide a better and modern living environment however, they also believe that mining and forestry does not invest on their town’s infrastructure and development. They noted that it is ‘unfortunate’ that the city relies on the mining company to develop but ‘it is what it is’ because Gällivare developed as a town because of the mines.

The 2nd perspective – Reindeer and Nature first – is based on the prerequisite that nature, biodiversity, local culture and human wellbeing will improve once reindeer grazing lands recovers. Advocates agree that nature resources are limited and Gällivare cannot compensate for the overconsumption in all Europe and the entire western world or globally. They believe that there should be no more mines in the Sapmi, however existing mines can stay as they are but expanding should stop as it means more grazing lands will be destroyed

The third perspective, Industry growth is equivalent to community growth. Advocates allow economic dependence with the industries, particularly the mines. They believe that development of the industries is part of the development of the community and at the same time they are inclusive in decision making.

Advocates believe that mining companies should expand and operate as long as possible in so that locals have a secure livelihood. They reject the idea that There should be no more mines in Sapmi lands, unlike the 2nd perspective, because this is impossible as almost all of the land in Gällivare is Sapmi.

But what does our results mean? You see, successful policies are dependent on clear understanding of local people's perspectives, and delineating areas of agreement and conflict is crucial in the development of Gällivare, or any city.

We did this research to shed light on how different people think. We hope that this research somehow informs politicians as they move the development agenda along.

Gällivare's case is a testament that there are differing perspectives that needs to be considered in policies and decision making. The existence of these three different perspectives makes achieving a common goal to be challenging, either it be for Gällivare's growth, resource conservation or local benefit.

We must also take into consideration not to put too much pressure on Gällivare's resources and local community, since they are already heavily impacted by the green transition and climate change. Careful consideration of all perspectives by decision makers and participative way of adjusting future development with all involved interested actors is highly needed.

Global drivers. Local consequences

Appendix IV. Current perspectives and future scenarios on Westfjords development

This video is part of the videobox developed in the Arctichubs project:

Global drivers, local consequences: Tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic “hubs”

Current perspectives and future scenarios on Westfjord development

Nestled in the remote northwest corner of Iceland, Westfjords is experiencing rapid redevelopment of both fish farming and tourism. Industries aim to expand production, claiming positive economic impact for the communities.

But what do local people really think about the development in Westfjords, now and in the future?

To answer our question, we conducted Q methodology and future scenario workshops

Q methodology is a mixed method to study perspectives. It is done in 5 steps. First, determining the universe of opinions regarding Westfjords’ development based on expert interviews and literature review. Then we selected sample opinions focusing fish farming and tourism. Third, we tested 32 sampled opinions or Q-set with a group of participants- these are experts, authorities, local citizens and special ones. We then conducted an online and in-person survey. A total of 22 participants sorted and ranked them in an inverted grid to most agree to disagree. Once all the survey were collected, we ran statistical analysis composed of different steps, after which we extracted two perspectives

Westfjords’ Current perspectives

The first perspective: Improve local infrastructure to support tourism growth.

Advocates believe that infrastructure in the Westfjords such as roads, accommodation, recreation facilities need to be improved so that tourism will be more developed therefore increasing jobs and income, which will bring back the region’s vitality. Advocates also trust in their government to make the best decision for the region’s development

The second perspective: Insufficient investment hampers local growth

Advocates also believe that infrastructure should be improved but highlighted that it is the lack of funding and investment that hinders the development of industries in the region. However, advocates do not believe that the government have Westfjords’ best interest in decision making.

Westfjords’ Future perspectives

Using existing data and the knowledge from private and public sector, experts and local residents, we created future stories or scenarios about how would Westfjords look like in the future? Through a series of activities such as interviews, discussions, future workshops and map-based survey, we found 6 future scenarios

The first future scenario 'Transportation infrastructure development is a pivotal factor for the region's future prosperity'. It highlights a future where better transportation infrastructure improves the connections between settlements, making the road system more reliable, resilient and safe, supporting the overall development of the area and making it more attractive for new businesses and services.

The second scenario 'Community-based controlled development of industries' highlighted a future, where land uses and industries' development is controlled by the community through public participation. This means limited business growth with longer consultation phases, more local acceptance and citizen empowerment, transparency and communication by economic players and possibly the implementation of more sustainable practices.

The third scenario 'Interaction of economy, infrastructure and transportation' sees a future, where strong global companies in aquaculture coexist with small family-owned tourism companies which are confronted to lack of robust infrastructure and reliable, year-round transportation system, affecting their competitiveness and viability.

In the fourth scenario 'The viability of the communities', demographic issues such as a widening gender gap, threatens the viability of the region, and the economy is mainly concentrating in fisheries and aquaculture, and foreign residents are not actively participating in the communities, and a more sustainable development of communities is needed.

The fifth scenario 'Aquaculture-driven community development' sees a future where the development of aquaculture and fish processing facilities increases and provides more revenues for the municipalities, attracting more residents. Beyond a certain population threshold, the diversity of employment and business opportunities increases, but there is a high reliance on fisheries and aquaculture, exposing the community to market fluctuations, potential resource overuse and environmental factors.

The sixth scenario 'Tourism-driven community development' highlights a future, where tourism is being developed through the consolidation and expansion of infrastructure, services, and available activities related to natural and cultural heritage of the area. The capacity of the area increases to accommodate more cruise ships in the region as well as more exclusive products. Employment in the area is more diverse but remains highly seasonal and low-paid, which is a limit to attract permanent residents and new families.

But what does our results mean? The current perspectives align with those of the future perspectives in a way that now and the future, Westfjords' aim for economic development led by the community needs. As such, these should be reflected in current policies and regulations for the municipality to truly develop

Westfjords presents a case where local people wants more economic growth, inclusivity and transparency. Global drivers like increase in tourism, and increase fish farming or aquaculture production is visible and is actually preferred to benefit the local community, now and in the future.

Unlike the other hubs we have discussed in this videoseries, Westfjords' industries are not as established as Varangerfjord or Gällivare, hence the economic growth is being prioritized, nevertheless, this doesn't mean that local people and the industries do not care for the environment, it's just because of economic needs that caring for nature, takes a backseat.

Global drivers. Local consequences

Appendix V. Current perspectives on European Arctic development

This video is part of the videobox developed in the Arctic Hubs project: Global drivers, local consequences: Tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development of industrial and cultural Arctic “hubs”

Current perspectives on European Arctic development

The European Arctic is commonly viewed as an untouched wilderness with minimal human impact due to its harsh weather and sparse population. However, it has a rich history of economic activities like mining, forestry, and fish farming, which have reached industrial scale and significantly rely on the exploitation and use of Arctic natural resources. Moreover, the seemingly untouched nature or wilderness has also become the basis for tourism development. All of these economic activities impact the only Indigenous people in Europe – Sami and Inuits as well as their traditional livelihood such as reindeer herding, hunting and fishing.

While the industries provide economic benefits, increase town vitality and improve infrastructure in the Arctic region, they also cause environmental and cultural harm. And it is the local people and indigenous communities that are particularly exposed to the cumulative pressures from different resource-intensive industries, therefore we ask, what do local people really think about the development in the European Arctic?

To answer our question, we conducted Q methodology and future scenario workshops

Q methodology is a mixed method to study perspectives. It is done in 5 steps. First, determining the universe of opinions regarding Arctic development based on expert interviews and literature review. Then we selected sample opinions focusing on fish farming, forestry, mining, tourism and indigenous activities. Third, we tested 36 sampled opinions or Q-set with a group of participants—these are experts, authorities, local citizens and special ones that stand to gain or lose whatever the result of the development. We then conducted an online and in-person survey. A total of 35 participants sorted and ranked them in an inverted grid to most agree to disagree. Once all the survey were collected, we ran statistical analysis composed of different steps, after which we extracted three perspectives

Current perspectives on the European Arctic development

The first perspective: Extractive industries harm the environment and local culture

Advocates believe that extractive industries degrade the environment local cultures, livelihoods and their only aim is to maximize profits. They believe that the resource utilization in the Arctic region is done in an irresponsible and unsustainable way. In particular, they believe that green transition can also be dubbed as a dark transition in the Arctic. Advocates are also skeptic about decision making systems in the Arctic as they are not transparent and inclusive.

The second perspective: Utilizing resources ensures local growth

BOKU
UNIVERSITY

Advocates believe that by utilizing the natural resources of the Arctic region, municipalities secure their welfare ambitions. This means localities and their workforce are developed which is the key factor in development. However, advocates believe that all profits from extractive industries should stay within the local communities and not be sent to the 'South' or capitals.

Advocates of the 2nd perspective is the opposite of the 1st perspective as they believe that there is no need for stronger environmental protection in the Arctic region

The third perspective: Local community comes first

Advocates believe that industries must gain the trust of the local people and should consider the needs of the Arctic communities first and foremost. They are not against development but makes a point that development should allow traditional land uses to flourish including indigenous people way of life, their culture and traditions.

Industries must support local economies to be accepted by the local community, and that trust from the local communities is the key to all progress

But what does our results mean?

We did this research to shed light on how different people think, which influences how they act. This is important for authorities and decision makers since they are the ones designing policies and regulations. Knowing points of agreement and conflicts can move the negotiation and discussions positively to be more inclusive and transparent

What becomes obvious from this study and from the other videos which is part of this videobox series is that there are different perspectives on the development of the Arctic region.

How these can be integrated into co-created policies can pose a challenge not only to the Arctic region but also to the whole world, as what happens in the global north affects the global south

With the Arctic's rapid development, it's crucial to be mindful of not overwhelming the region's resources and the local communities, especially considering the substantial impact of the green transition and climate change. Decision makers must carefully weigh all perspectives and engage all relevant stakeholders in adapting future development plans.

Global drivers. Local consequences

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